

1 **Title:**

2 **Climate change impacts on soil organic carbon stocks of Mediterranean agricultural areas: a case study in**
3 **Northern Egypt**

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16

17 **Abstract**

18 Mediterranean agricultural areas are characterised by low soil C contents and as a consequence they are often
19 degraded and highly vulnerable to environmental changes. Climate change is predicted to have a large impact
20 upon these areas but they may be key for mitigation of its effects given their potential for soil C sequestration.
21 Several approaches have been proposed to evaluate climate change impacts on soil organic C stocks being soil
22 carbon models amongst the most effective tools to assess C stocks, dynamics and distribution and to predict
23 trends under climate change scenarios. In this study, we applied the CarboSOIL model and global climate
24 models to predict and analyse the effects of short (2030), medium (2050) and long term (2100) climate
25 changes on soil organic C contents at standard soil depths of 0-25, 25-50 and 50-75 cm in a Mediterranean arid
26 area (El Fayoum, Northern Egypt) for different land use types. The validation of CarboSOIL with field data
27 proved the consistency of the model and overall decreases of soil organic C contents in the upper soil layers
28 are expected in the short (2030), medium (2050) and long (2100) term. However, intensity of these changes
29 will depend on the land use type and our results suggest that agricultural land uses depending on irrigation will

30 be particularly vulnerable to losses of soil organic C stocks. We found larger decreases of soil organic C
31 contents in the upper soil layers and increases in the deeper layers under climate change scenarios. This study
32 demonstrates the importance of assessing soil organic C contents and dynamics along the soil profile and the
33 potential for soil C sequestration particularly in the subsoil. The methods used in this research can be applied
34 in other Mediterranean areas with available information on soil, land use and climate.

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36 Keywords:

37 CarboSOIL model; land use; land use change; semi-arid areas; soil carbon sequestration; global change.

38

39 1 Introduction

40 Despite the on-going debate on climate change as a result of increased emission of greenhouse gases (GHG)
41 into the atmosphere, there is scientific evidence that that the global climate is changing and that human
42 activity contribution is significant (Princiotta and Loughlin, 2014; Smith et al., 2016). Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is
43 the single most important GHG derived from human activity and responsible for 74% of global warming over
44 the past decade (Canadell and Schulze, 2014). Soil organic C (SOC) plays a key role in the C cycle since it
45 represents twice the amount of atmospheric C and 70-75% of the Earth's terrestrial pool (Lal, 2004; Brevik et
46 al., 2015). Even minor changes in the SOC pool can have a critical effect in the global C cycle, influencing the
47 atmospheric concentration of GHG in the atmosphere and therefore the global climate change (Smith, 2004a).
48 At the same time, soils can act as sinks for atmospheric CO₂ by sequestration of organic C (Von Lützow and
49 Kögel-Knabner, 2009) and are able to store C for long periods of time (Brevik and Homburg, 2004). It has been
50 reported that 89% of mitigation potential by agricultural management depends on SOC sequestration (Smith
51 et al., 2008). However, large uncertainty remains concerning the scope of these feedbacks and considerable
52 differences exist among prediction models (Friedlingstein et al., 2006). A more accurate quantification of the
53 response of terrestrial C, with a large proportion deriving from the soil C pool, is therefore crucial for
54 understanding the Earth's response to global warming and climate change (Lal, 2004; Muñoz-Rojas et al.,
55 2013).

56 Most of the recent research on SOC sequestration has been conducted in temperate-humid and tropical
57 environments and there is a lack of studies in Mediterranean areas (Ruiz Sinoga et al., 2012). Climate in these
58 regions is characterized by seasonal dryness, and many subareas are classified as arid or semi-arid (Muñoz-
59 Rojas et al., 2012; Albaladejo et al., 2013). In Mediterranean agricultural systems, levels of productivity are
60 typically low and there is a largely dependency on irrigation (Aguilera et al., 2013a; Ouda et al., 2016). As a
61 consequence of their low SOC contents, these areas are often degraded and vulnerable to environmental
62 changes, and climate change is predicted to have a large impact upon them (Metz, 2007). Most of the
63 prediction models suggest higher temperatures and decreases in rainfall in Mediterranean areas compared to
64 other systems, which could promote higher decomposition rates of SOC (Davidson and Janssens, 2006).
65 However, recent research underpins the key role of Mediterranean areas in mitigation of climate change given

66 their potential for SOC sequestration by adopting adequate management practices (Smith, 2004b; Aguilera et
67 al., 2013a). Besides its role in the C cycle, the presence of organic C in the soil is crucial to the quality and
68 functionality of the soil ecosystem, improving physical, chemical and biological quality of the soil (de Graaff et
69 al., 2015; Lal et al., 2011; Brevik et al., 2015; Smith et al., 2016). Thus, increasing organic C in these
70 environments with appropriate land management techniques or land use changes could be also beneficial for
71 soil erosion control, soil fertility and, ultimately, food production (Aguilera et al., 2013a; Hontoria et al., 2004;
72 Perras-Alcántara et al., 2015a). Biogeochemical cycles of N, P, S and other plant nutrients are driven by SOC
73 dynamics (Alexander et al., 2015), and benefits can be obtained even after relatively short periods of time
74 (Wasak and Drewnik, 2015).

75 Several approaches have been applied to evaluate climate change impacts on SOC stocks being soil carbon
76 models amongst the most effective tools to assess SOC stocks, dynamics and distribution and to predict trends
77 under climate change scenarios (Falloon and Smith, 2003; O'Leary et al., 2015). However, the absence of
78 adequate models that are validated and calibrated with field data and monitoring challenges the development
79 of appropriate integrated practices in response to climate change impacts (Stringer et al., 2012). Moreover, to
80 predict future changes in SOC stocks, Global Climate Models (GCMs) are indispensable to simulate global
81 climate since they provide simulations of atmospheric general circulation and project climate variables such as
82 temperature and precipitation in future climate scenarios (Mitchel et al., 2004). These GCMs use available
83 information on future GHG emissions generated by socioeconomic scenarios (Mertz et al., 2007).

84 A number of soil carbon models have been used in the Mediterranean region in the last years, including
85 CENTURY (Parton et al., 1987) or RothC (Coleman and Jenkinson, 1996). These models have been applied in
86 different areas to assess the effects of management practices on SOC stocks (Alvaro-Fuentes et al., 2007) and
87 also the impacts of climate change (Alvaro-Fuentes et al., 2012; Francaviglia et al., 2012; Mondini et al., 2012).
88 But, despite the critical influence of soil depth on SOC stocks (Jobbágy and Jackson, 2000; Willaarts et al.,
89 2015) most of the available research on soil carbon modelling focus on the upper soil layer (topsoil), and only
90 few studies include deeper sections of soil in their analyses (Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2012, 2015a, 2015b; Perras-
91 Alcántara et al., 2015b). Large amounts of SOC may be stored in subsoil layers, particularly in temperate
92 grasslands where it has been estimated that 59% of the SOC stocks accumulates between 20 and 100 cm
93 depth (Jobbágy and Jackson, 2000). Therefore, even minor alterations in these subsoil SOC stocks could have

94 extensive impact on the balance of the entire SOC pool (Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2013). Moreover, several models
95 assume that mechanisms and processes controlling SOC dynamics are similar in both topsoil and subsoil, but
96 recent research has shown that driving factors of SOC differed across the vertical section of the soil profile
97 (Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2013; Parras-Alcantara et al., 2015b; Willaarts et al., 2015).

98 There is strong relation between environmental conditions and C accumulation in the soil (Muñoz-Rojas et al.,
99 2012; Ruiz-Sinoga et al., 2012) although there are significant gaps in the knowledge of the effects that climate
100 change will cause at different soil depths (Jobbágy and Jackson, 2000; Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2015a). Our main
101 objective was to apply the CarboSOIL model (Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2013) and GCMs to predict and analyse the
102 effects of short (2030), medium (2050) and long term (2100) climate changes on SOC contents at standard soil
103 depths of 0-25, 25-50 and 50-75 cm in a Mediterranean arid area (El Fayoum, Northern Egypt) for different
104 land use types. With that aim, the CarboSOIL model was previously validated in the study area by testing the
105 model predictions for current scenarios with measured SOC stocks in the field. Due to aridity, water sources of
106 the Nile are much more important than rainfall for agricultural production in irrigated desertland (Agrawala et
107 al., 2004) and accordingly, climate change scenarios considered in this work also include projections of
108 irrigation water inputs from the Nile River.

109 2 Methods

110 2.1 Model description

111 CarboSOIL was developed to analyse SOC stocks and C sequestration capacity of natural and agricultural
112 systems under different climate and land use change scenarios. This model is a component of the agro
113 ecological decision support system (DSS) MicroLEIS (De la Rosa et al., 2004) that was designed to assist
114 decision makers on specific agro-ecological issues related to land productivity and degradation. MicroLEIS DSS
115 was developed as a knowledge-based approach incorporating a set of information tools, linked to each other
116 and has been globally used land evaluation in different areas worldwide such as Spain (Anaya-Romero et al.,
117 2011), Iran (Shahbazi et al., 2010) or Mexico (Aguilar-Duarte et al., 2011). CarboSOIL consists of three main
118 modules or subcomponents for SOC accounting at different standard depths: (i) CarboSOIL25 (0-25 cm), (ii)
119 CarboSOIL50 (25-50 cm) and (iii) CarboSOIL75 (50-75 cm). The required input parameters to run the model

120 include data that are generally easily obtained in soil surveys: (a) climate variables (mean winter/summer
121 temperature and annual precipitation), (b) site variables (elevation, slope, dominant erosion processes, type of
122 drainage), (c) physical and chemical soil properties (pH, total N, cation exchange capacity, sand/clay content,
123 bulk density and field capacity), and (d) land use type; in total 15 independent variables and SOC as predictor
124 variable (Table 1). The model is described in detail in Muñoz-Rojas et al. (2013).

125 2.2 Study area

126 El-Fayoum depression (Northern Egypt, Figure 1) is located at coordinates 29° 02′-29° 35′ N and 30° 23′-31°
127 05′ and includes six districts with a total surface of 1,776 km². The area is a natural endorheic depression on a
128 limestone plateau (Eocene). It offers a great potential for agriculture due to water supply from Bahr Yousef
129 canal, a tributary of Nile (Abd-Elmabod et al., 2012). Climate is classified as hot desert (BWh; Peel et al., 2007)
130 with annual rainfall between 8 and 11 mm, mostly concentrated between December and March and potential
131 evapotranspiration varies between 3.1 and 10.3 mm/day, 6.8 mm/day on average (Climatological Survey
132 Department of El-Fayoum Governorate, 2009). Mean monthly temperature ranges between 11.6 (January) and
133 28.2 °C (July), with mean annual temperature 20.9 °C.

134 According to Soil Survey Staff (2014), Vertic Torrifuvents is the dominant soil subgroup, covering an area of
135 760 km² (42.79% of the study area). Other important soil subgroups are Typic Haplocalcids (421 km², 23.70%)
136 and Typic Torrifuvents (141 km², 7.94%). The rest of soil subgroups (Typic Haplogypsid, Typic Haplosalid and
137 Typic Torripsammets) are found in small marginal areas (11.45%), as described by Haroun (2004) and Ali
138 (2005).

139 2.3 Soil sampling and analyses (site, soil and land use data)

140 Twenty eight points covering four agricultural land use types were selected, classified according to Muñoz-
141 Rojas et al. (2011): complex cultivation patterns (CC), fruit trees and berries (FT), permanently irrigated areas
142 (PI) and olive groves (OG). At each point, land use type and site characteristics were recorded: elevation (masl),
143 slope (%), type of drainage (poor, water is eliminated so slowly that soil remains wet for long periods;
144 moderate, water is eliminated slowly, so that the profile remains wet for short periods; and excessive, water is
145 lost very rapidly).

146 Soil samples were collected at each point at standard depths (0-25, 25-50 and 50-75 cm), air-dried (48 h at
147 room conditions) and sieved (2 mm) before analysis. The following chemical soil properties were determined:
148 soil acidity (pH) in saturated paste (Thomas, 1996), salinity (electric conductivity) in saturated paste (Rhoades,
149 1996), SOC content by the acid-dichromate potassium and titration method (Walkley and Black, 1934), cation
150 exchange capacity (CEC; Summer and Miller, 1996).

151 For texture analysis, air-dried soil subsamples were pre-treated with H₂O₂ (6%) to remove organic matter and
152 soluble salts, dried in the oven to obtain the initial weight, dispersed with a sodium hexametaphosphate
153 solution, and mechanically shaken. The sand fraction (0.05-2 mm) was removed from the suspension by wet
154 sieving and then fractionated by dry sieving; the fine silt (0.002-0.02 mm) and clay (<0.002 mm) fractions were
155 determined by the pipette method (Kilmer and Alexander, 1949). Coarse silt (0.02-0.05 mm) was calculated as
156 the difference between 100% and the sum of the sand, clay, and fine silt percentages. Finally, soil bulk density
157 was determined by the core method (Blake and Hartge, 1986) and field capacity according to Saxton and Rawls
158 (2006).

159 2.4 Climate data sources and projections

160 Current climate data (mean temperature of December, January and February; mean temperature of June, July
161 and August; and mean annual rainfall) were obtained from El-Fayoum Weather Station and introduced into the
162 CDBm database of MicroLEIS DSS (De la Rosa et al., 2004) for processing (Table 3). Data on irrigation water
163 supply from the Nile River (via Elahoun and Hassan Wasef canals) were provided by the Directorate of
164 Irrigation of El-Fayoum. The area cultivated in El-Fayoum covers 1,566 km² and a total of 1,427 mm year⁻¹ of
165 irrigation water reach the depression (ASRT, 2009)

166 Climate change scenarios were obtained from Global Climate Models (GCMs) based on the scenarios proposed
167 by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the Intergovernmental Panel on
168 Climate Change (IPCC) (Agrawala et al., 2004) (Table 3). These GCMs predict changes in annual and seasonal
169 (winter and summer) temperatures and rainfall in the short-, medium-and long-term (2030, 2050 and 2100,
170 respectively) using MAGICC/SCENGEN, a coupled gas-cycle/climate model (MAGICC; Raper et al., 1996) that
171 drives a spatial climate change scenario generator (SCENGEN; Santer et al. 1990). MAGICC has been the

172 principal model used by IPCC to generate projections of future global temperatures and sea level rise
173 (Houghton et al., 2001).

174 Two climate projections were used in this study: one that consider a progressive decrease in water inputs
175 based on the GCM estimates of temperature and precipitation changes for Egypt ('E') and another one that
176 considers a little increasing in the source waters from the Nile ('N') (Table 3), with both projections having
177 increments in the temperature under climate change scenarios. All scenarios selected were based on the IPCC
178 B2 SRES scenario (Nakicenovic et al., 2000) that assumes a world of moderate population growth and
179 intermediate level of economic development and technological change.

180 2.5 Model validation and application

181 To validate the model in the study area, we analysed the differences between measured and predicted values
182 of SOC stocks at each standard soil layer (0-25, 25-50 and 50-75 cm) in the current scenario using different
183 statistical parameters: linear regression, the Pearson correlation coefficient R^2 , the root mean square error
184 (RMSE) and the Nash-Sutcliffe modelling efficiency factor (EF; Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970). Lower values of RMSE
185 indicate less residual variance and therefore less difference between observed and modelled SOC contents.
186 When both RMSE and the standard deviation have the same order of magnitude, the model is accurately
187 describing the data (Smith and Smith, 2007). Regarding the EF, the closer this parameter is to 1, the more
188 accurate the model is. Pearson correlations were considered significant at the $P < 0.001$ level.

189 After validating the model in the current scenario, CarboSOIL was applied in the 28 soil units using the selected
190 climate scenarios (Table 3). Changes between current and predicted SOC contents were determined for each
191 land use type at the different soil depths.

192 3 Results

193 3.1 Soil characterization under different land use types

194 On average, SOC content varied between 0.35 ± 0.06 (OG) and $0.86 \pm 0.16\%$ (CC) at the upper soil layer (0-25
195 cm) and generally decreased with depth under all land use types (Table 2). Total showed a similar trend, with
196 average contents 0.02-0.04% (0-25 cm), 0.01-0.03% (25-50 cm) and 0.00-0.03% (50-75 cm). Soil pH varied in a

197 narrow range, between 7.8 and 8.5. CEC did not show great variations in depth, but varied among different
198 land uses. For the 0-25 cm layer, CEC was 6.4 ± 1.0 (OG), 21.2 ± 4.9 (CC), 26.9 ± 3.6 (PI) and 40.9 ± 2.2
199 $\text{cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$ (FT). According to Soil Survey Division Staff (1993), soil texture was sandy clay loam (CC), clay (FT),
200 clay loam (PI) and loamy sand-sandy loam (OG). Finally, bulk density and field capacity varied between 1.2 and
201 1.5 g cm^{-3} and 0.2 and 0.5%, respectively.

202 3.2 Model validation and predicted soil organic carbon content changes

203 Measured values of SOC contents were strongly correlated with predicted estimates for all depths (Figure 2) in
204 the study area. The R^2 coefficient varied between 0.975 at 0.25 cm and 0.9879 at 50-75 cm ($p < 0.001$). The
205 RMSE was 3.64 (0-25 cm), 0.99 (50-75 cm) and 1.82 (50-75 cm), in all cases below SD (14.65, and 10.27 and
206 10.18, respectively). The EF ranged between 0.966 (0-25 and 25-50 cm) and 0.970 (50-75 cm).

207 An overall decrease of SOC contents in the upper soil layers (0-25 and 25-50 cm) is expected for both
208 scenarios, 'E' and 'N' (Figure 3), although the intensity of changes will be conditioned by land use type.
209 Predicted changes of SOC contents in the 0-25 cm layer ranged from -4.4 to -2.6% under CC and PI land use
210 types and -1.1 and 0.6% under FT. In contrast, expected changes in SOC contents in the 0-25 cm layer under OG
211 showed an irregular trend, with values ranging between -2.8 (2100 'N' scenario) and 2.1% (2100 'E' scenario).
212 In the 25-50 cm layer, progressive decreases were predicted under all land use types between current date
213 and 2100, especially under OG (-2.7 and -4.8% in 2100 under 'E' and 'N' scenarios, respectively).

214 In contrast, strong continuous increases were predicted in the 50-75 cm layer under all land use types, with
215 similar trends under both scenarios. In 2100, SOC contents are expected to increase under CC (3.2%), FT
216 (between 2.6 and 2.7% in 'E' and 'N' scenarios, respectively), PI (2.9%) and OG (between 6.9 and 7.0% in 'E'
217 and 'N' scenarios, respectively) in the deepest studied soil layer (50-75 cm).

218 4 Discussion

219 4.1 Validation of CarboSOIL model under current conditions

220 Modelling SOC is often associated to uncertainty derived from lack of accuracy in the input data,
221 inconsistencies in the structure of the model or the spatial resolution and/or inappropriate calibration or

222 validation of model parameters in the study area (Scharlemann et al., 2014; O’Leary et al, 2016). Well-designed
223 calibration models are crucial to simulate changes in measured SOC stocks but in general, there is an absence
224 of field surveys with enough measurements to validate predictions of SOC models. These models are often
225 calibrated based on limited measurements that do not include estimates in depth underestimating the carbon
226 pool in the subsoil (Jandle et al., 2014).

227 In this study, we validated the predicted current values of SOC obtained with CarboSOIL with measured values
228 in the field and our results proved the ability of CarboSOIL to predict SOC for different land use types and
229 environmental conditions at different sampling depths. The statistical parameters obtained for each soil depth
230 were similar to those obtained by Muñoz-Rojas et al. (2015a) in their study in agro-silvo-pastoral
231 Mediterranean systems, where they applied CarboSOIL to predict SOC changes in 12 climate scenarios. They
232 reported values of 0.977, 8.42, 0.63 (0-25 cm), 0.990, 5.07, 0.98 (25-50 cm) and 0.762, 5.88 and 0.93 (50-75
233 cm) for R^2 , RMSE and EF, respectively. In Muñoz-Rojas et al. (2013), Spearman’s R coefficients were used to
234 test the efficiency of CarboSOIL in a study conducted in Southern Spain. Their results showed that R Spearman
235 values ranged from 0.9898 and 0.990 and were significant at $P < 0.01$.

236 According to Jandl et al. (2014), there are roughly two types of models used for estimating SOC stocks at
237 regional scales: (i) process-based mechanistic models commonly used for development of ecological theories,
238 and (ii) simple models able to identify drivers of SOC dynamics and perform projections at coarser scales. In
239 general, available SOC models show different levels of complexity and, whereas some require a large amount
240 of input data, others can be used with commonly available data such as CarboSOIL (Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2013).
241 Although CarboSOIL may not be able to explain complex mechanisms in the soil system, here we show that the
242 model is consistent and measured values are well correlated with those predicted by the model.

243 4.2 Prediction of soil organic C contents under different climate change 244 scenarios

245 Our results suggest that land use type is a key factor to consider in the assessment of global change impacts on
246 SOC in Mediterranean and arid areas, in agreement with a number of studies (Albaladejo et al., 2013;
247 Machmuller et al., 2015; Willaarts et al., 2015). According to the predictions obtained in this study, different
248 responses can be expected for soils under different land use types. SOC contents below OG, PI and CC are

249 sensitive to climate change impacts in El Fayoum and are expected to decrease in the first 50 cm of soil depth.
250 In the case of OG, the impact on 0-25 and 25-50 cm soil layers is moderate for 2030 and 2050 E and N
251 scenarios, but large under 2100 N scenarios. In contrast, SOC in the 50-75 cm layer is expected to show a
252 general increase, especially under OG by 2100. Expected changes in SOC content from soils under FT are small
253 in 2030 and 2050 scenarios, but larger by 2100. Different authors have suggested that warming may contribute
254 to a general decrease in organic C content from intensively managed soils (e.g by tillage or permanent
255 irrigation) (Smith, 2004b) which has been attributed to increased mineralization rates (Albadalejo et al., 2013).
256 Although it has been reported that drought conditions contribute to decreased decomposition rates by
257 reducing the thickness of water films, thus inhibiting diffusion of extracellular enzymes and soluble organic-C
258 substrates and lowering substrate availability (Davidson and Janssens, 2006), irrigation may limit the impact of
259 drought. Expected reductions of SOC in the 0-25 and 25-50 cm layers of soils under FT are smaller and might
260 be explained as increased biomass production and higher organic residue inputs under this land use type, as
261 suggested by Balkovic et al. (2011).

262 The effects of temperature on the SOC dynamics and mechanisms can change with depth (Willaarts et al.,
263 2015) and several studies have found a decreasing correlation between temperature and SOC content with
264 depth (Jobbagy and Jackson, 2000; Abadalejo et al. 2013; Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2013). A higher sensitivity to
265 climate of SOC in the upper layers could explain the expected decrease of SOC stocks under increased
266 temperatures, particularly in areas with high levels of agricultural intensification (Smith et al., 2016). In
267 contrast, our results predicted increased SOC stocks in the deeper soil section (50-75 cm) under all land use
268 types considered, which suggest that different factors such as texture or lithology (Oyonarte et al., 2008) seem
269 to control SOC stocks in deep soil layers. This hypothesis has been also supported by Jobbagy and Jackson
270 (2000) and Abadalejo et al. (2013), who observed that the impact of air temperature is smaller than clay
271 content in depth. Other authors (Yang et al., 2010) have related these gradients of SOC along the soil profile
272 with differences in the labile and recalcitrant C, reporting decreases in the labile fractions while the
273 recalcitrant forms increases in depth. Some studies have reported a high sensitivity of labile C to temperature
274 versus stable C (Thornley and Cannell, 2001), which might be critical in future climate scenarios with higher
275 temperatures. However, recent works have shown contradictory results and this issue is still far from resolved
276 (Conant et al., 2011).

277 Although results showed that positive changes are generally expected in SOC at the 50-75 cm layer, larger
278 accumulations were predicted for soils under rainfed olive-cropped soils. Positive SOC accumulations were also
279 predicted in OG soils under reduced rainfall in 2030, 2050 and 2100 ('E' scenario) and increased water
280 irrigation inputs in 2030 ('N' scenario). Olive groves are drought tolerant (Tugendhaft et al., 2016) and do not
281 depend on irrigation, which can explain the differences in SOC stocks dynamics in the upper soil layer for the
282 two sets of climate projections. Olive groves, which are less intensively managed systems compared to PI or CC
283 areas, have the lowest SOC contents in the current scenario and, consequently, can have a large potential as
284 SOC sinks, particularly in the subsoil. Previous studies have also suggested that the strategies for SOC
285 sequestration in Mediterranean areas should be focused on the deeper soil layers (Albaladejo et al., 2013),
286 although the complexity of the diverse available options can be different depending on the specific conditions
287 of the area (Willaarts et al., 2015).

288 4.3 Implications for the future of Mediterranean areas and their contribution 289 to mitigate climate change

290 The future of agricultural systems in Mediterranean arid areas such as N Egypt will largely depend on changes
291 in the amount and frequency of rainfall and temperature regimes (Ouda et al., 2016), which may cause
292 important social and economic impacts (Bisaro et al., 2014). Increases in SOC stocks in these areas with
293 typically low SOC contents would improve the quality of the soil which at the same time could have a critical
294 effect on crop productivity under more extreme climate conditions (Aguilera et al., 2013a; Smith et al., 2016).
295 A number of recommended management practices (RMP) have been suggested to increase SOC stocks in
296 Mediterranean cropping areas given the key role that land use type plays on SOC changes (Francaviglia et al.,
297 2012; Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2012). The adoption of RMPs can therefore be an effective option for C
298 sequestration in soils and bring additional environmental and socioeconomic benefits (Smith, 2004b;
299 Albaladejo et al., 2013). It is remarkable that globally, the potential for soil C sequestration of RMPs has been
300 estimated at $0.9 \pm 0.3 \text{ Pg C year}^{-1}$ (Lal, 2004). These RMPs can include zero or reduced tillage, mulching and
301 residue management or composting, application of inorganic fertilizers and manure, improved rotations, use
302 of improved crop varieties, and water management (Alexander et al., 2015; Jandl et al., 2007; Smith, 2004b).

303 Many studies highlight the large heterogeneity and complexity of Mediterranean agricultural areas with
304 different patterns in SOC distribution which is related to the history of land use and management during the
305 last decades (Muñoz-Rojas et al., 2015b; Novara et al., 2015). Thus, RMPs should be specific to the
306 particularities and specific conditions of each area, avoiding the adoption of global solutions (Willaarts et al.,
307 2015). Mediterranean agricultural areas are particularly vulnerable to climate change since most climate
308 models predict higher-than-average increases in temperature and generalised decreases in precipitations in
309 most of these areas (IPPC, 2007) which consequently will lead to reduced water availability. This water deficit
310 will be even more critical in dry areas like N Egypt since Egyptian agriculture is based in a large extent on
311 irrigation and is highly dependent on the supply of water from the Nile river (Agrawala et al., 2004; Abd-
312 Elmabod et al., 2012). Recommended management for C sequestration in these areas should focus in
313 appropriate water management including adequate surface irrigation and drainage systems (Ouda et al.,
314 2016). Our results showed that land uses that depend on irrigation are particularly vulnerable to losses of SOC
315 stocks; therefore these RMP can not only help to improve plant productivity and production of SOC but also to
316 optimise energy used for irrigation that is largely associated to GHG emissions (Aguilera et al., 2013b).

317 5 Conclusions

318 The application of CarboSOIL in N Egypt under current and future climate change scenarios allowed us to
319 analyse changes in SOC stocks for different land use types and soil depths in future climate conditions. The
320 validation of the model by contrasting predicted versus measured values of SOC contents proved the
321 consistency of CarboSOIL. An overall decrease of SOC contents in the upper soil layers (0-25 and 25-50 cm) is
322 expected in the short (2030), medium (2050) and long (2100) term, although the degree of intensity of these
323 changes will depend on the land use type. Our results showed that agricultural land uses depending on
324 irrigation will be particularly vulnerable to losses of soil organic C stocks. We found larger decreases of soil
325 organic C contents in the upper soil layers and increases in the deeper layers under climate change scenarios.
326 This study demonstrates the importance of assessing soil organic C contents and dynamics along the soil
327 profile and the potential for soil C sequestration particularly in the subsoil. The methods used in this research
328 can be applied in other Mediterranean areas with available information on soil, land use and climate.

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537

538 **Tables and figures**

539 Table 1. CarboSOIL output (dependent variable) and input variables, units and data sources.

540 Table 2. Soil input variables (mean \pm SD) under different land use types (complex cultivation patterns, fruit
541 trees and berries, permanently irrigated areas and olive groves) and at different depths (0-25, 25-50 and 50-75
542 cm).

543 Table 3. Climate input variables. TDJF: winter temperature (average of the months December, January and
544 February); TJJA: summer temperature (average of the months June, July, August); PRPT: annual precipitation.
545 Scenario E considers a progressive decrease in water inputs based on the GCM estimates of temperature and
546 precipitation changes for Egypt. Scenario N considers a little increase in the source waters from the Nile river.
547 Changes in temperature and precipitation have been determined according to the OECD predictions (Agrawala
548 et al., 2004).

549 Figure 1. Study area (El-Fayoum depression, Egypt).

550 Figure 2. Measured versus predicted values of SOC stocks (Mg ha⁻¹) with CarboSOIL. Linear regression and
551 statistical parameters: R² (Pearson correlation coefficient), RMSE (root mean square error), EF (modelling
552 efficiency).

553 Figure 3. Changes in SOC stocks in climate change scenarios predicted by CarboSOIL. Land use types: CC
554 (complex cultivation patterns), FT (Fruit trees and berries), PI (Permanently irrigated areas) and OG (olive
555 groves).

556

Table 1. CarboSOIL output (dependent variable) and input variables, units and data sources.

Variable type	Variable name	Code	Unit	Source and reference
Dependent variable	Soil organic C	SOCC	Mg ha ⁻¹	Haroun (2004) and Ali (2005)
Climate	Total (annual) precipitation	PRPT	mm	Climatological Survey Department, Egypt (2009)
	Winter temperature	TDJF	°C	
	Summer temperature	TJJA	°C	
Site	Elevation	ELEV	m	Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) image, 2011
	Slope	SLOP	%	
	Drainage	DRAI	-	Haroun (2004) and Ali (2005)
	Soil erosion	SERO	-	
Soil	Nitrogen	NITRO	%	
	pH	PHWA	-	
	Cation exchange capacity	CEXC	cmol(+)kg ⁻¹	
	Sand	SAND	%	
	Clay	CLAY	%	
	Bulk density	BULK	g cm ⁻³	
	Field capacity	FCAP	%	
Land use	Land use/cover	LULC	-	

Table 2. Soil input variables (mean \pm SD) under different land use types (complex cultivation patterns, fruit trees and berries, permanently irrigated areas and olive groves) and at different depths (0-25, 25-50 and 50-75 cm).

Land use	Depth (cm)	n	Organic C (%)	Total N (%)	pH	Cation exchange capacity (cmol(+)kg ⁻¹)	Sand (%)	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	Field capacity (%)
Complex cultivation patterns	0-25	7	0.86 \pm 0.16	0.04 \pm 0.01	7.9 \pm 0.1	21.2 \pm 4.9	48.2 \pm 8.1	22.5 \pm 3.0	29.3 \pm 5.7	1.3 \pm 0.4	0.3 \pm 0.1
	25-50	7	0.48 \pm 0.11	0.02 \pm 0.01	8.1 \pm 0.2	22.8 \pm 4.3	46.2 \pm 6.7	21.5 \pm 1.8	32.4 \pm 5.0	1.4 \pm 0.1	0.3 \pm 0.2
	50-75	7	0.56 \pm 1.10	0.03 \pm 0.01	8.1 \pm 0.2	19.8 \pm 3.9	49.6 \pm 5.8	21.9 \pm 2.1	28.5 \pm 3.8	1.4 \pm 0.1	0.3 \pm 0.2
Fruit trees and berries	0-25	3	0.84 \pm 0.27	0.04 \pm 0.01	8.4 \pm 0.3	40.9 \pm 2.2	21.5 \pm 5.1	22.3 \pm 5.8	56.2 \pm 4.8	1.2 \pm 0.1	0.5 \pm 0.1
	25-50	3	0.62 \pm 0.22	0.03 \pm 0.01	8.5 \pm 0.2	41.6 \pm 2.5	21.5 \pm 6.5	23 \pm 3.4	55.5 \pm 5.3	1.3 \pm 0.1	0.5 \pm 0.2
	50-75	3	0.61 \pm 0.22	0.03 \pm 0.01	8.4 \pm 0.2	41.4 \pm 1.9	20.7 \pm 4.4	23.8 \pm 1.1	55.6 \pm 5.3	1.3 \pm 0.1	0.5 \pm 0.1
Permanently irrigated areas	0-25	11	0.86 \pm 0.14	0.04 \pm 0.01	8.1 \pm 0.1	26.9 \pm 3.6	38.3 \pm 6.5	23.5 \pm 2.2	38.1 \pm 4.8	1.3 \pm 0.1	0.3 \pm 0.3
	25-50	11	0.65 \pm 0.09	0.03 \pm 0.00	8.1 \pm 0.1	27.3 \pm 3.6	36.7 \pm 6.6	23.7 \pm 2.2	39.6 \pm 4.8	1.3 \pm 0.3	0.4 \pm 0.3
	50-75	11	0.61 \pm 0.09	0.00 \pm 0.00	8.1 \pm 0.1	27.2 \pm 3.6	37.4 \pm 6.8	23.7 \pm 2.4	38.8 \pm 4.9	1.3 \pm 0.4	0.3 \pm 0.2
Olive groves	0-25	7	0.35 \pm 0.06	0.02 \pm 0.00	7.8 \pm 0.1	6.4 \pm 1.0	83.1 \pm 3.7	6.3 \pm 1.6	10.6 \pm 2.4	1.5 \pm 0.1	0.2 \pm 0.0
	25-50	7	0.25 \pm 0.04	0.01 \pm 0.00	7.8 \pm 0.1	8.7 \pm 2.6	79.7 \pm 6.4	9.4 \pm 3.6	10.9 \pm 3.1	1.5 \pm 0.1	0.2 \pm 0.1
	50-75	7	0.24 \pm 0.04	0.01 \pm 0.00	7.8 \pm 0.1	9.5 \pm 3.2	78.7 \pm 6.2	9.9 \pm 3.5	11.3 \pm 3.0	1.5 \pm 0.1	0.2 \pm 0.1

Table 3. Climate input variables. TDJF: winter temperature (average of the months December, January and February); TJJA: summer temperature (average of the months June, July, August); PRPT: annual precipitation. Scenario E considers a progressive decrease in water inputs based on the GCM estimates of temperature and precipitation changes for Egypt. Scenario N considers a little increase in the source waters from the Nile river. Changes in temperature and precipitation have been determined according to the OECD predictions (Agrawala et al., 2004).

Date	Scenario E			Scenario N		
	Average, °C (Change, ΔT)	Average, °C (Change, ΔT)	Average, mm (Change, %)	Average, °C (Change, ΔT)	Average, °C (Change, ΔT)	Average, mm (Change, %)
Current	13.7	28.9	1,427	13.7	28.9	1,427
2030	14.5 (0.8)	30 (1.1)	1,353 (-5.2)	14.7 (1.0)	29.9 (1.0)	1,449 (1.5)
2050	14.9 (1.2)	30.6 (1.7)	1,319 (-7.6)	15.2 (1.5)	30.4 (1.5)	1,457 (2.1)
2100	15.8 (2.1)	31.8 (2.9)	1,239 (-13.2)	16.2 (2.5)	31.5 (2.6)	1,480 (3.7)

Figure 1. Study area (El-Fayoum depression, Egypt).

Figure 2. Measured versus predicted values of SOC stocks (Mg ha^{-1}) with CarboSOIL. Linear regression and statistical parameters: R^2 (Pearson correlation coefficient), RMSE (root mean square error), EF (modelling efficiency).

Figure 3. Changes in SOC stocks in climate change scenarios predicted by CarboSOIL. Land use types: CC (complex cultivation patterns), FT (Fruit trees and berries), PI (Permanently irrigated areas) and OG (olive groves).